

Relationship between leaf chlorophyll content and rice yield. Beaumont, Texas.

Chlorophyll reading	Expected yield increase (t/ha)	Expected net return to topdressing N (\$)
20	1.4	93
30	0.7	37
35	0.4	17
40	0.1	(-3)

topdressed with 45 kg/ha 2 wk before and at panicle differentiation. Net income due to topdressing decreased as leaf chlorophyll increased.

When chlorophyll readings were near 39 and higher, there was no economic advantage to topdressing N (assuming urea = \$165/t, application cost = \$8.64/ha, and rice value = \$8/cwt).

The chlorophyll meter (model SPAD-501 developed by Minolta) does have limitations: initial cost = \$1400. But fertilizing a 40-ha field with 45 kg N/ha also = approximately \$1400. Another limiting factor is that leaf chlorophyll can be influenced by P, Zn, and Fe deficiencies; low temperature; rice variety; growth stage; and herbicides. □

Economy in combining fertilizer N with green manure in lowland rice

G. Shukla, P. C. Pandey, P. S. Bisht, and P. Lal, Agronomy Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, Uttar Pradesh, India

We studied the integrated effect of organic + inorganic N on rice yield and N use efficiency and recovery during wet season 1988. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. The soil is silt loam classed as Aquic Hapludoll, with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq/100 g, and 0.1% total N.

For green manure, 50-d-old crops of *Sesbania rostrata* and *S. aculeata* were chopped and incorporated into the top 15 cm soil at 10 and 20 t/ha, respectively, 1 wk before transplanting. Farmyard manure (FYM), 20 t/ha fresh weight basis, was incorporated 1 mo before transplanting. Pant Dhan 4 was sown 1 Jun and transplanted 11 Jul. All plots received 17.6 kg P, 24.2 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha before transplanting. N was applied per treatment (see table).

Yield with *Sesbania* alone equaled yield with 90 kg N as prilled urea (PU). *Sesbania* with 30 kg N as PU increased the grain yield 9%, which was significantly higher than that with 90 kg N as PU alone and equaled yield with 120 kg N as PU or USG.

Highest N use efficiency and apparent N recovery was with *Sesbania* alone.

S. rostrata proved no better than *S. aculeata*, probably because it had only half the biomass. □

Effect of organic and inorganic N source on yield, N uptake, N use efficiency, and apparent N recovery in rice.^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

Treatment	Time and rate of N			Grain yield (t/ha)	N uptake (kg/ha)			N use efficiency (kg grain/kg N applied)	Apparent N recovery (%)	
	Basal through	PU			Total N (kg/ha)	Grain	Straw			Total
		6-7	DBPI							
	GM	PU								
Control	0	0	0	0	3.8	54	24	78	-	
USG	0	80	40	120	5.8	95	61	156	17	
PU	0	80	40	120	5.7	93	46	139	16	
PU	0	50	40	90	5.4	82	51	133	18	
SA ^b + PU	60	20	40	120	6.1	101	55	155	19	
SR ^b + PU	40	40	40	120	6.1	100	55	155	19	
FYM ^b + PU	50	30	40	120	6.1	100	45	145	19	
SA + PU	60	30	0	90	6.0	100	44	144	24	
SR + PU	40	30	0	70	5.8	96	42	138	29	
FYM + PU	50	30	30	110	5.0	77	38	118	11	
SA	60	0	0	60	5.3	87	46	113	25	
SR	40	0	0	40	5.2	75	33	108	38	
LSD (0.05)					0.4	6	7	11	-	-

^aGM = green manure, USG = urea supergranule (46% N), PU = prilled urea (46% N), SA = *Sesbania aculeata* (2% N, 80% moisture), SR = *Sesbania rostrata* (1.75% N, 83% moisture), FYM = farmyard manure (0.5% N, 50% moisture). ^bN content in sesbania and FYM was analyzed, The remaining N was applied through PU to meet the basal requirement of 80 kg N/ha. The rest or 1/3 of 120 kg N was applied at 6-7 d before panicle initiation (DBPI).

Effect of deep-placed urea supergranules (USG) with limited green manure on transplanted rice yield

S. S. Dhane, R. R. Khadse, and V. H. Patil, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth (KKV), Karjat, Maharashtra State 410201, India; and N. K. Savant, International Fertilizer Development Center (IFDC), P. O. Box 2040, Muscle Shoals, Alabama 35662, USA

The amount of green manure available in small rainfed rice farmers' fields is likely to be very limited. In 1988 wet season, we compared the effect of deep-placed USG and split-applied prilled

urea (PU) alone and in combination with limited amounts of *Gliricidia sepium* leaves on rainfed transplanted rice.

The 11 treatments were laid out in 15-m² plots on the RARS farm, Karjat, in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil was clay loam with pH (1:2.5 soil:water) 7.0 and cation exchange capacity 30 meq/100 g. All plots received 17 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 33 kg K/ha as potassium chloride.

PU (38 kg N/ha) was applied 50% broadcast and incorporated before transplanting and 50% topdressed before panicle initiation. USG (1-g pellets) was hand placed about 10 cm deep during

line transplanting, one pellet every four hills (15 × 20 cm). Quantities of gliricidia green leaves (containing 2.7% N oven-dried basis) to supply 0, 1, 1.5, 2, and 2.5 t green manure/ha were spread uniformly over freshly puddled soil before line transplanting. Karjat-184 was transplanted (3-wk-old seedlings) 7 Jul and harvested 12 Oct.

Deep-placed USG significantly increased grain and straw yields (see table). Deep-placed USG at 38 kg N/ha plus green manure increased grain yield more than split-applied PU. □

Effect of USG and PU with limited gliricidia green manure on rainfed transplanted rice yield. ^a Maharashtra, India, 1988 wet season.

Urea N (kg/ha)	Treatment		Yield (t/ha)		Tillers/hill (no.)
	Green manure t/ha	kg N/ha	Grain	Straw	
0	0	0	2.8 c	3.1 d	7.9 e
38 (PU)	0	0	3.0 c	3.2 d	9.7 de
38 (PU)	1	6.3	2.9 c	3.4 d	12.5 abc
38 (PU)	1.5	9.5	2.9 c	3.2 d	10.3 cde
38 (PU)	2	12.6	3.2 bc	3.8 cd	11.1 bcd
38 (PU)	2.5	15.8	3.5 b	4.5 bc	11.9 bcd
38 (USG)	0	0	3.8 ab	4.7 bc	13.0 ab
38 (USG)	1	6.3	3.9 a	5.1 ab	13.5 ab
38 (USG)	1.5	9.5	4.0 a	5.7 a	12.5 abc
38 (USG)	2	12.6	4.2 a	5.5 ab	14.6 a
38 (USG)	2.5	15.8	3.9 a	5.2 ab	15.1 a

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Integrated nutrient management in irrigated rice

M. R. Patel, N. P. Chauhan, S. A. Patel, and J. G. Patel, Gujarat Agricultural University, Main Rice Research Station, Nawagam, Gujarat, India

We studied the integrated effect of organic and inorganic sources of N on growth and grain yield of rice variety GR11 during 1987 wet season. Eight fertilizer combinations were tested (see table).

The test soil was sandy loam with a pH of 7.3, EC 3.5 dS/m, 0.065% total N, 68.5 kg available P/ha, and 332.8 kg available K/ha.

P and K were applied basally; N as ammonium sulfate was applied in four equal splits; basal and at tillering, panicle initiation, and dough stage.

Azolla was inoculated at 1 t/ha 10 d after transplanting (DT). Because of an erratic rainy season, water was not impounded and azolla grew very poorly. The azolla mat was incorporated 30 DT.

Sesbania aculeata was incorporated 1 d before transplanting.

Before incorporation azolla had 2.8% N, 0.48% P, and 3.2% K; *S. aculeata* had 2.5% N, 0.64% P, and 1.0% K.

Delayed planting due to failure of the monsoon and use of brackish irrigation water from a bore well decreased yields.

Grain yield with *S. aculeata* + 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha and *S. aculeata* + 0-20-20 kg NPK/ha were significantly higher than all other treatments except 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha alone and *S. aculeata* + azolla + 0-20-20 kg NPK/ha. □

Effect on rice yield of N applied during reproductive phase

P. C. Pandey, P. S. Bisht, and P. Lal, Agronomy Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, Uttar Pradesh, India

In the subtropical climate of north India, rice grown with recommended best N split (1/2 basal, 1/4 at tillering, 1/4 1 wk before panicle initiation) or standard split (2/3 basal, 1/3 1 wk before panicle initiation) has luxuriant vegetative growth but the canopy turns light green during ripening. We tested supplying a larger proportion of N during reproductive stages (1 wk before panicle initiation, at booting, and at heading), at 120 and 180 kg N/ha. The field experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications in wet season 1988 at Pantnagar (29° N, 79° 29' E, 244 m).

Soil was silt loam with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq/100 g soil, 0.1% total N, 13.9 kg available P/ha (Olsen), and 202 kg available K/ha (NH₄OAc extraction).

Pant Dhan 4 (134 d duration) was sown 1 Jun and transplanted 5 Jul with basal application of 17.6 kg P, 24.2 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha.

Effect of organic and inorganic sources of N on yield and panicles/m². Nawagam, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Biomass (t/ha) incorporated
Control	0.8	108	—
0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	0.8	128	—
40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	2.0	196	—
Azolla + 0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	1.0	119	3.2
Azolla + 40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	1.9	171	1.8
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + 0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	3.3	307	26.4
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + 40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	3.7	300	22.7
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + azolla + 0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	2.8	240	24.9
80-17.6-33.2 kg NPK/ha	3.1	258	+1.5
LSD (0.05)	1.1	75	—